

Impact of duration and missing data on the long-term photovoltaic degradation rate estimation

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ABSTRACT

Accurate quantification of photovoltaic (PV) system degradation rate (R_D) is essential for lifetime yield predictions. Although R_D is a critical parameter, its estimation lacks a standardized methodology that can be applied on outdoor field data. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the impact of time period duration and missing data on R_D by analyzing the performance of different techniques applied to synthetic PV system data at different linear R_D patterns and known noise conditions. The analysis includes the application of different techniques to a 10-year synthetic dataset of a crystalline Silicon PV system, with emulated degradation levels and imputed missing data. The analysis demonstrated that the accuracy of ordinary least squares (OLS), year-on-year (YOY), autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) and robust principal component analysis (RPCA) techniques is affected by the evaluation duration with all techniques converging to lower R_D deviations over the 10-year evaluation, apart from RPCA at high degradation levels. Moreover, the estimated R_D is strongly affected by the amount of missing data. Filtering out the corrupted data yielded more accurate R_D results for all techniques. It is proven that the application of a change-point detection stage is necessary and guidelines for accurate R_D estimation are provided.

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1. Introduction

Reliability and durability are the main influential factors for safeguarding high-performing photovoltaic (PV) systems. In this domain, knowledge of the underlying degradation and ageing of PV materials is valuable for manufacturing improvements and the introduction of new durable materials. Accurate information of the long-term degradation is necessary in order to predict the electricity output over time and find engineering solutions to effectively improve reliability and increase the remaining useful lifetime (RUL). Inaccurate degradation rate (R_D) estimations (defined as the gradual decline of performance that is typically expressed in %/year) result in erroneous predictions of the future energy yield and hence, the levelized cost of energy (LCoE). A sensitivity analysis

based on a Monte Carlo simulation and theoretical degradation curves demonstrated that the R_D is the third most important factor influencing the LCoE, after the discount rate and capital cost [1].

Even though performance warranties provided by most manufacturers are extending beyond a 25-year lifetime period, field experience has shown that PV modules degrade because of a multitude of factors. For this reason, the nature, physical mechanisms and calculation of R_D in fielded PV systems has been the target of numerous research efforts [1–20]. Several factors may affect the R_D extraction including location (or climate), technology, data measurement fidelity, measurement accuracy and precision rendering the calculation process non-trivial [7,14,19,21].

The fact that PV module performance warranties, provided by the manufacturers, are not possible to be based on end-of-life testing (e.g., flash test on year 25–30), it strengthens the need for establishing a validated method for accurately and confidently estimating R_D from field data. In addition, it is often expected to specify modules again in the laboratory, which is a laborious

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method that requires a common understanding between the manufacturer and the system operator regarding sampling. Currently, there is no standardized method for calculating the R_D of PV systems from field performance data and the difficulty in identifying the most appropriate technique or method, relies on the fact that the resulting degradation value is unknown or hidden within faults, seasonal events, noisy data and uncertainties of measurements. In order to consider the influence of seasonal losses (e.g., thermal [22] and spectral [23]), failures [24] and other trend-based losses (e.g., soiling [25] and shading [26]) on the resulting long-term degradation estimates, another term was proposed to account for this gradual (and overall) power decline namely the performance loss rate (PLR) [2,4,7,15].

The limiting factor of all prior long-term R_D assessments is the lack of extensive validation because the actual value of degradation is unknown, hence the accuracy of each method cannot be assessed. Irrespective of the existing technological difficulties and limitations, previous research efforts that calculate PV system R_D focused on the application of different statistical and comparative techniques such as the ordinary least squares (OLS), the classical series decomposition (CSD), the seasonal and trend decomposition using Loess (STL), the year-on-year (YOY), the autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) and the robust principal component analysis (RPCA) that extract the trend from measured performance time series and assume linearity [12,13,27–36]. Most prior studies employed the OLS approach mainly due to its simplicity [4,7,15,16,19,33,35]. Even though the simplicity of the OLS-based regression techniques renders them applicable for outdoor PV system performance time series, the trend extraction is highly prone to errors caused by seasonality, non-constant trends, outliers and missing data. Recent studies focused on deseasonalization techniques such as CSD and STL in order to reduce seasonal fluctuations [4,7,19,28]. Other studies focused on reducing and extracting the underlying structure of the data (components that show the most substantial variance in the data) by applying the RPCA to calculate the degradation rate [1,8,31]. Another estimation technique is the YOY (that identifies the median slope among all lines passing through the data points) which has been proposed as an alternative to regressive models [37,38]. Specifically, the YOY method is used as a powerful and practical central-difference estimator for assessing the median degradation of PV systems by comparing a multitude of trends from day-to-day or month-to-month over each year [17]. Seasonal effects such as soiling, shading and temperature bias are minimized by using this method.

Most of the aforementioned approaches have already been translated to open-source tools available to serve the purpose of a reproducible method. These include the “RdTools” from NREL [39], which is a Python package for degradation and soiling rate estimation and “PVplr”, which is an R library built as a part of the IEA-PVPS Task 13 study on the determination and uncertainty of PLR calculation [40]. These tools provide useful functionality and a common framework for calculating the R_D or PLR, however the extent to which the different pipeline techniques and models perform when applied to outdoor performance datasets that include faults and noisy conditions is yet not fully explored. To this end, the impact of missing data on the underlying degradation rate is not fully qualified and there is no approach to provide ways to differentiate degradation under these conditions. This contributes to the diversity of values reported in the literature by analyzing outdoor system performance measurements since the results depend on the applied methodology and data pipeline but also the performance behaviour of the time series (presence of noisy conditions, fault events and degradation pattern).

Data quality assurance is required for the implementation of a universal and standardized method for calculating degradation

rates exclusively from outdoor PV performance measurements [41]. Even though data quality constitutes the foundational block for reliability analytics, only a few studies address issues that focus on data processing and quality control tools [41–44]. Jordan and Kurtz [45], discussed the impact of data filtering and showed how it can result in irreproducible R_D estimations; they also proposed some guidelines to aid the data filtering process when no baseline measurements exist. Furthermore, as part of the IEA-PVPS Task 13 research on PLR determination, a comparison between several common approaches, including the effects of different data filtering criteria and power predictive models, resulted to 20 distinct PLR calculations [13] highlighting further the issue of irreproducibility. Despite these studies, this is the first time that all commonly used R_D time series techniques are compared side-by-side against datasets of known behavior (synthetic datasets with emulated degradation) while also investigating the impact of time series duration and missing data on the resulting R_D .

Moreover, all commonly employed long-term PV system R_D algorithms assume a constant and linear degradation pattern when applying various statistical/comparative techniques on PV performance time series. However, the linearity assumption is often violated either in the infant or wear-out phase of a system's lifetime. Recent studies demonstrated that nonlinear power loss behavior is usually observed in the field depending on the module technology and degradation patterns [1,11,46]. Field experience demonstrated that this underlying assumption of linearity is not always valid since degradation modes can occur at any period. For this reason, R_D approaches need to be coupled with statistical change-point techniques in order to detect such trend-based loss events and appropriately apply subsequent techniques to evaluate the degradation pattern. Recent work presented the application of change-point analysis to detect changes in the slopes of PV trends of monthly performance ratio (PR) time series and apply linear fits to the different segments to compute the corresponding rates [11,47]. Such models are important not only for improving financial modeling accuracy but also for condition-based maintenance strategies [48]. However, even though the application of change-point techniques can shed light into the nonlinear behavior exhibited in the degradation patterns, the exact impact of missing data on the degradation trend and value, is yet not investigated and can only be assessed using outdoor data with accurate fault logs and regular operation & maintenance (O&M) practices or, synthesized datasets.

The applicability and accuracy of different R_D techniques and data analysis pipelines under missing data conditions is commonly ignored and not yet fully explored. Thus, this paper contributes to the formulation of usage guidelines for different statistical/comparative degradation techniques under such missing data conditions. In this work, synthetic PV performance datasets with known R_D and missingness were generated for testing different techniques and filtering in order to provide useful information with respect to the following research questions:

- How do different R_D pipeline methods perform when applied to outdoor performance PV system time series of known linear degradation patterns?
- How to differentiate the underlying degradation pattern and quantify the rate?
- How does time series duration influence the accuracy of the estimated R_D ?
- How do missing data affect the degradation estimation accuracy and confidence?

2. Methodology

The analysis to evaluate how different long-term R_D techniques perform when applied to PV system performance time series of pre-known linear degradation trends and missing data is presented in this section. The process includes a sequence of extensive validation steps to determine R_D by applying different time series analytics to the constructed synthetic datasets. The synthetic datasets were constructed using historical weather measurements and metadata from a “replica” test-bench PV system with monocrystalline Silicon (mono-c-Si) PV modules. The system is installed at the outdoor test facility (OTF) of the Research Centre for Sustainable Energy FOSS in Nicosia, Cyprus (Köppen–Geiger-Photovoltaic climate classification BK: desert climate with very high irradiation) [49]. More specifically, the sensitivity of the R_D techniques at different emulated linear degradation rate patterns (from 0.2%/yr to 2%/yr at intervals of 0.2%/yr), evaluation period duration and presence of missing data, was evaluated. In parallel, different missing data events were randomly imputed to the raw power datasets and monthly performance ratio (PR) time series in order to emulate commonly exhibited communication and data acquisition (DAQ) errors. The applied methodology is illustrated in

Fig. 1.

2.1. Experimental setup

The historical data used for constructing the synthetic dataset and testing the sensitivity of R_D techniques in the presence of missing data were acquired from a test-bench mono-c-Si PV system installed at the outdoor test facility at the FOSS Research Centre in Nicosia, Cyprus (see Fig. 2). The system is in operation and high-quality data (at a resolution of a second and recording interval of 1-, 15-, 30- and 60-min average) are acquired since 2006.

The performance of the test-bench PV system and the prevailing weather conditions were recorded and stored with the use of a DAQ monitoring platform according to the requirements set by the IEC 61724-1 [43]. The test-bench PV system comprises of 5 mono-c-Si PV modules of rated power 205 W_p that are installed in an open-field arrangement at an inclination angle of 30°. The modules are connected in series to form a string of nominal capacity 1.025 kW_p at the input of a grid-connected smart inverter. The system was selected amongst all others since it did not exhibit any failures and was further tested using indoor maximum power determination techniques in year 8 of operation. The infrastructure

Fig. 1. Flowchart of performed analytical steps to test the sensitivity of R_D techniques in the presence of noise.

Fig. 2. Outdoor test facility at the FOSS Research Centre in Nicosia, Cyprus.

is also equipped with a weather station for monitoring in-plane solar irradiance (G_I), wind direction (W_a), wind speed (W_s), and ambient temperature (T_{amb}). The PV system operational measurements include the array current (I_A), voltage (V_A) and power (P_A), as measured at the output of the PV array (DC side). AC energy measurements at the output of the inverter are also acquired using an energy meter whereas the module temperature (T_{mod}) is recorded using a resistance temperature detector (RTD). The system was continuously monitored and high-quality data were acquired over a 10-year period. All the installed sensors and the associated measurement uncertainties (acquired from manufacturer datasheets and calibration files) are summarized in Table 1 [50].

Both the PV system and the installed pyranometer were periodically cleaned to minimize any soiling effects (e.g., seasonal cleaning and after heavy dust deposition events). All installed sensors were systematically calibrated as specified by the manufacturers and periodic cross-checks against sister sensors (other pyranometers and temperature sensors installed in close proximity) were conducted in order to identify sensor drifts [1].

2.2. Actual and synthetic performance datasets

The electrical and weather data were recorded at a resolution of a second and aggregated as 15-min averages over a 10-year period (June 2006–May 2016) for the test-bench PV system. The yearly in-plane solar irradiation in Nicosia, Cyprus ranged from 1967 kWh/m²/yr to 2109 kWh/m²/yr, over the 10-year evaluation period. The exhibited monthly total in-plane irradiation over the 10-year evaluation period in Nicosia, Cyprus is provided in Fig. 3a. Similarly, the average monthly ambient temperature in Nicosia, Cyprus, depicted in Fig. 3b, was 19.5 ± 0.5 °C. Both the irradiation and ambient temperature plots exhibit a relatively monotonic trend behavior.

Fig. 3. Monthly (a) Total in-plane irradiation and (b) Average ambient temperature in Nicosia, Cyprus over the 10-year evaluation period.

In order to generate synthetic datasets that “replicate” the real system operation, the 15-min meteorological measurements from Nicosia, Cyprus and system-specific metadata were used as inputs to the Sandia PV Array Performance Model (SAPM) [51] available in *pvlib-python* [52]. Different R_D were then introduced to the PV performance time series by linearly declining the simulated current output at ranges from 0.2%/yr to 2%/yr at intervals of 0.2%/yr. The degradation was applied on the current output rather than voltage because aluminum back surface field (Al-BSF) technologies are dominated by losses in short-circuit current [53]. The R_D range was selected to reflect commonly exhibited degradation values listed from previous review studies [7,16]. The raw datasets were then normalized using the PR and aggregated monthly. The constructed synthetic performance datasets of the test-bench system with the emulated degradation levels up to 2%/yr at increments of 0.2%/yr, are shown in Fig. 4.

The impact of dataset duration on the calculated R_D value was investigated by applying the analytical techniques to the monthly PR datasets with emulated degradation levels of 0.4%/yr, 1%/yr and 2%/yr; no missing data were emulated. These datasets were selected in order to provide results at different degradation category levels denoted as low = 0.4%/yr, moderate = 1%/yr and high = 2%/yr.

Furthermore, to examine the impact of missing data on the degradation estimation accuracy and confidence, artificial missing data points were imputed completely at random to the synthetic datasets using a nonparametric imputation method based on

Table 1
Technical information of DAQ system, sensor network and uncertainty.

Parameter	Manufacturer model	Uncertainty
Data acquisition	Delphin Top message	±0.01% of measuring range
Ambient temperature	Theodor Friedrich 2030	±0.6% (0.15 °C at 25 °C)
In-plane irradiance	Kipp Zonen CM21-CV 2	±2% expected daily accuracy, ±20 W/m ² for 1000 W/m ²
DC voltage	Muller Ziegler Ugt	±0.5%
DC current	Muller Ziegler Igt	±0.5%
AC energy	Muller Ziegler EZW	±1%

Fig. 4. Synthetic performance dataset with emulated R_D from 0.2 to 2%/yr at increments of 0.2%/yr for the test-bench mono-c-Si PV system.

random forest algorithm [54]. The missing data points were introduced by first selecting a missing data rate from 10% to 50% (steps of 10%) and then utilizing the “prodNA” function available in “missForest: Nonparametric Missing Value Imputation using Random Forest” R package [54] that introduces NA values until the target missing data rate was reached. This R package artificially introduces missing values using iterated random forests; it uses a random forest trained on the observed values of a table to predict the missing values. The missing data imputation process was repeated 10 times for each missing data rate (10%, 20%, 30%, 40% and 50%), resulting in 50 datasets. The PR timeseries from each missing data rate were then averaged for the performance analysis.

The emulated R_D of 1%/yr 10-year time series was selected as the baseline for the noise condition analysis. More specifically, the missing values (indicated with NA) were randomly imputed (replacement of actual data-point with NA value) to the raw power measurements and aggregated monthly PR values. The imputed missing values represent communication errors, short-term failures of DAQ systems and sensors (and not PV plant downtime and outage periods). Before commencing the time series analytical techniques, the NA values were filtered out. Subsequently, the 1%/yr monthly PR time series was re-constructed and the long-term R_D was calculated using the investigated analytical techniques in the presence of various shares of missing values.

2.3. Data quality and filtering

An important step in the analysis pipeline of the R_D methodology was the application of data quality routines (DQRs) on the actual and synthetic “raw” datasets of the test-bench PV system based on Livera et al. [41]. Throughout this step, the “raw” measurements were validated in order to ensure high-quality for the subsequent analysis. The implemented DQRs include algorithms for detecting invalid data (duplicate records, missing and erroneous data), outliers and outages [41]. All detected invalid data-points were filtered out from the dataset.

2.4. Degradation pattern diagnostics

An important step in the analysis was the application of statistical change-point techniques to evaluate the detection extent of

nonlinear degradation patterns [11,47]. This is a very important step in order to safeguard that the appropriate analytical techniques are employed to capture the underlying degradation pattern. To this end, a change-point detection technique using the pruned exact linear time (PELT) method [55], was applied to the synthetic univariate monthly PR time series in order to detect changes in the mean. The PELT method is based on an algorithm for optimal partitioning of data and change-points are detected by minimizing the sum of a penalized cost function [56].

Change-points (or breakpoints) are abrupt variations in the investigated time series data and may represent transitions between different states and the occurrence of nonlinear dynamics. In particular, the applied technique quantifies changes in the variability of PR time series and yields information whether the extracted trend is defined by different segments. Each detected segment is analyzed in a linear manner in order to compute the corresponding degradation rates.

2.5. Time series analytics

A variety of statistical techniques for calculating the long-term R_D , namely OLS, CSD, YOY, STL, ARIMA, and RCPA [1,4,7,8,19,28,31,37,38], were applied to the constructed monthly PR synthetic time series of the test-bench PV system. The best ARIMA model (derived by the “auto.arima” function [57] available in “forecast” R package [58]) for the 10-year PR synthetic time series was the (0,1,1) (1,1,0). A benchmarking evaluation of applying the different techniques to the synthetic datasets with the emulated degradation levels was then performed in order to highlight the technique that converged to the actual R_D value according to the timeframe of the analysis.

The time series techniques were applied to the different constructed synthetic datasets in order to investigate their robustness in calculating R_D at various durations and missing data rates.

3. Results of comparative analysis based on synthetic datasets

3.1. Validation of pattern and degradation estimation without any missing data

An important step before commencing the application of any statistical techniques for R_D extraction is to verify that the degradation pattern is indeed linear and that there are no change-points in the trend. The reason behind this is that the detection of change-points reflects to nonlinearities of the degradation trend caused by exhibited faults or nonlinear degradation mechanisms.

In this investigation the PELT change-point detection technique was applied to the synthetic monthly PR datasets to detect multiple change-points in the mean of the PR time series. The PELT algorithm requires as input features the penalty values to avoid over fitting (e.g., identifying noise as change-points). In this work, the change-points for a range of penalties (CROPS) were selected. The minimum and maximum penalty values were set to 0.001 and $\log_{10}(n)$, respectively, where n is the number of months in the given time series. In order to estimate the significance of the detected change-points using PELT, the small sample hypothesis t -test was used [59]. The synthetic datasets demonstrated a linear underlying degradation since no change-points were detected.

Fig. 5 summarizes the absolute percentage error (APE) between the emulated and calculated R_D values obtained when applying the different statistical/comparative techniques to the synthetic monthly PR datasets over the 10-year period for all emulated R_D levels (no missing data were emulated). Qualitatively, it is evident that STL and CSD yielded substantially more accurate results compared to the remaining models, exhibiting median APE of 3%

Fig. 5. APE of R_D calculated by applying different commonly employed time series analytical techniques to the synthetic monthly PR datasets, over the evaluation period.

and 3.8%, respectively. Moreover, the RPCA technique always provided overestimated results at all degradation levels exhibiting also the highest residual dispersion amongst the investigated techniques. Conversely, the ARIMA and OLS techniques exhibited the lowest residual dispersion as shown in Fig. 5.

3.2. Impact of dataset duration on degradation rate estimation without any missing data

Fig. 6 shows the R_D deviations (ΔR_D) between the emulated and estimated R_D obtained when applying the different statistical techniques to the monthly PR datasets. The results showed that the accuracy of most techniques converged within ΔR_D intervals of $\pm 0.2\%/yr$ after 5 years. In particular, the decomposition models (STL and CSD) and YOY exhibited high accuracies even after 3 years and irrespective of the degradation level, demonstrating that these techniques are robust to the impact of seasonality on the underlying trend. Conversely, the R_D accuracy for ARIMA and OLS improved after 5 years of data were analyzed, rendering the robustness of these techniques a function of the time series period irrespective of the degradation level. Additionally, the divergence of the R_D results calculated when applying RPCA at higher durations and high emulated degradations from the actual values, depicted in Fig. 6c, provide evidence that this technique is affected by both high R_D values and the duration. With respect to the confidence intervals, the results showed that the statistical uncertainty is reduced with the increasing number of data (or years).

3.3. Impact of missing data on long-term degradation rate estimation

The impact of missing data on the calculated R_D was evaluated by randomly imputing missing values (NA) to the raw power dataset and the aggregated monthly PR of the emulated R_D of 1%/yr 10-year time series at shares from 10% to 50%.

Fig. 6. ΔR_D of the different statistical/comparative techniques compared to the emulated R_D levels of (a) 0.4%/yr, (b) 1%/yr, (c) 2%/yr.

3.3.1. Test case with random missing values on raw datasets

The obtained results, depicted in Fig. 7, demonstrate that the increasing amount of missing data affects the accuracy and confidence of the calculated degradation. The statistical uncertainty of most techniques (OLS, RPCA, STL and YOY) increased as the shares of imputed missing values increased (all imputed NA values were filtered out rendering lower duration datasets), proving that the confidence of the models is affected by the corrupted data. At random noise levels of 10% all the applied techniques yielded accurate results with ΔR_D ranging between 0.04 and 0.26%/yr. However, at higher noise levels ($\geq 30\%$) the accuracy of all techniques decreased with the exception of RPCA. The RPCA technique provided the highest accuracies exhibiting ΔR_D in the range of 0.05–0.13%/yr. It is important to note that the fact that the imputed NA values were all filtered out from the datasets before commencing the time series analysis, demonstrates that filtering is applicable for half of the techniques at missing data rates of up to 20%; all techniques proved to be robust for missing data rates up to 10%.

3.3.2. Test case with missing values on aggregated PR time series

To evaluate the effect of random noise on aggregated data, missing values at shares from 10% to 50% and steps of 10% were imputed to the aggregated monthly PR of the emulated 1%/yr R_D time series. Accordingly, the R_D was calculated by first filtering out the missing values and then applying the time series techniques. The obtained results, illustrated in Fig. 8, demonstrate that when the percentage of random missing values is $\leq 10\%$, the applied statistical techniques provided accurate results with ΔR_D lower than 0.2%/yr. At missing data rates of 20–40% all techniques outperformed the YOY method that provided the highest ΔR_D values. Conversely, at 50% missing data rates all applied techniques overestimated the R_D value exhibiting differences over 0.6%/yr.

4. Performance verification based on actual PV system data

The applicability of the investigated techniques to accurately calculate the R_D was verified on the actual performance data of the test-bench mono-c-Si PV system and with the use of indoor standardized maximum power determination methods at standard test conditions (STC). Fig. 9a shows the histogram of monthly PR values of the test-bench mono-c-Si system exhibiting a mean value of 87% over the 8-year evaluation period. In order to verify whether the

Fig. 8. ΔR_D obtained by applying different commonly employed time series analytical techniques to synthetic monthly PR values with imputed random noise, over the 10-year evaluation period.

underlying degradation pattern of this system is linear and whether there is a change in the trend on the 8-year monthly PR time series, a change-point analysis using the PELT method was performed and a deflection point was detected on month 52, as depicted in Fig. 9b. This provides statistical evidence that the degradation pattern is nonlinear, hence stepwise regression (SR) was applied to the time series to calculate the degradation rate. More specifically, the yearly R_D was calculated over the first segment period (month 0–52, $R_D = 1.56\%/yr$) and then over the second segment (month 52–96, $R_D = 0.63\%/yr$), as depicted in Fig. 9b. Subsequently, the weighted average was taken to provide resulting R_D value of 1.14%/yr.

The long-term R_D values obtained by applying the different statistical techniques and two-step linear regression to the actual outdoor performance datasets, over the 8-year evaluation period are presented in Fig. 10. The long-term R_D result obtained by applying the SR technique to the actual performance data of the test-bench mono-c-Si PV system ($R_D = 1.14 \pm 0.48\%/yr$) exhibited the lowest error (18.6%) as compared to the degradation value obtained by utilizing standardized indoor methodologies ($R_D = 1.4\%/yr$). The linear statistical techniques provided degradation results between 0.5 and 1%/yr, which correspond to APE from 28.6% to 64.3%.

Even though, the analysis is commenced on a c-Si technology installed in the year 2006 the proposed methodology coupled with the change-point technique can be applied to any PV technologies exhibiting linear or nonlinear degradation over time.

5. Degradation analysis guidelines

In the scope of providing usage guidelines for the different statistical degradation techniques under random missing data, the main results obtained by analyzing the time series with emulated R_D of 1%/yr are summarized in Table 2. Overall, the results demonstrated that longer datasets reduced the statistical uncertainty in all models. For short-term evaluation periods (5-years) the highest calculated R_D deviations were obtained using the ARIMA and OLS techniques. Conversely, the calculated R_D deviations converged to lower values over the 10-year long-term evaluation for all techniques apart from RPCA at high degradation rates.

With respect to missingness in the raw power values, all the applied techniques yielded accurate results with ΔR_D ranging between 0.07 and 0.2%/yr at low noise shares (missing data rate $\leq 10\%$). At higher missing data rates ($\geq 30\%$) the accuracy of all

Fig. 7. ΔR_D obtained by applying different commonly employed time series analytical techniques to the synthetic raw power dataset with imputed random missing data, over the evaluation period.

Fig. 9. Actual performance of test-bench mono-c-Si system (a) Histogram of monthly PR values. The blue dashed line indicates the mean value. (b) Monthly PR over the evaluation period. The red dashed line indicates the detected change-point.

Fig. 10. Long-term R_D estimation using different statistical techniques for the test-bench mono-c-Si PV system based on actual outdoor performance datasets, over the 8-year evaluation period. The blue dashed line depicts the R_D obtained using indoor standardized maximum power determination procedures, over the 8-year period.

techniques decreased with the exception of RPCA.

In addition, for prolonged noise events affecting the aggregated

values (monthly PR time series) when the percentage of missing values is low ($\leq 10\%$ imputed noise level), the applied statistical techniques provided accurate results with absolute ΔR_D lower than $0.2\%/yr$. All techniques outperformed the YOY at missing data rates of 20–40%, while at 50% missing data rates all applied techniques overestimated the R_D value.

The application of a change-point detection stage to validate whether deflection points exist is a crucial step in degradation analytical methods. In the presence of a change-point, the two-step linear regression technique provides more accurate results compared to the application of time series analytics assuming a linear degradation pattern.

Finally, in order to provide more information about the combined impact of the R_D accuracy of the different methods in combination with the effect of incomplete data, the joint goodness score was calculated by averaging the accuracy of the R_D obtained for each technique over the 10-year period with the respective value at each missing data share (from 10% to 50%). The average values were then normalized to the true simulated R_D value of $1\%/year$ to obtain a goodness fit in the range of 0–1. The results are tabulated in Table 3.

6. Conclusions

Inaccurate R_D estimations result in erroneous predictions of the lifetime energy yield and LCoE of PV systems. To this end, accurate information of the long-term degradation is important in order to

Table 2

Usage guidelines for the different statistical degradation techniques. An accurate result is denoted at ΔR_D levels $\leq 0.2\%/yr$ while a less accurate result is denoted at ΔR_D levels $> 0.2\%/yr$.

Parameter	OLS	CSD	YOY	STL	ARIMA	RPCA
Very short-term period (<5-years)	Less accurate	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate	Less accurate	Less accurate
Short-term period (5-years)	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate
Long-term period (10-years)	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate
Long-period raw dataset low share noise ($\leq 10\%$ NA)	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate
Long-period raw dataset high share noise ($\geq 30\%$ NA)	Less accurate	Less accurate	Less accurate (accurate only at 30%)	Less accurate	Less accurate	Less accurate (only at 40–50%)
Long-period aggregated monthly PR low share noise ($\leq 10\%$ NA)	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate	Accurate
Long-period aggregated monthly PR high share noise ($\geq 30\%$ NA)	Less accurate	Less accurate	Less accurate	Less accurate	Less accurate	Less accurate
Nonlinear degradation	Less accurate	Less accurate	Less accurate	Less accurate	Less accurate	Less accurate

Table 3
Goodness score of combined impact of the R_D accuracy of the different methods in combination with the effect of incomplete datasets.

Technique	Combined R_D accuracy and 10% missing data rate	Combined R_D accuracy and 20% missing data rate	Combined R_D accuracy and 30% missing data rate	Combined R_D accuracy and 40% missing data rate	Combined R_D accuracy and 50% missing data rate
OLS	0.98	0.94	0.85	0.83	0.79
CSD	0.97	0.93	0.85	0.81	0.78
YOY	0.91	0.98	0.73	0.97	0.81
ARIMA	0.98	0.93	0.85	0.83	0.79
STL	0.98	0.94	0.85	0.83	0.79
RPCA	0.95	0.93	0.97	0.91	0.93

predict the electricity output over time and find engineering solutions to effectively improve reliability and increase the remaining useful lifetime. This renders necessary the analysis of how different long-term R_D techniques and models perform when applied to PV system performance time series of pre-known linear degradation trends and the presence of noise events.

To address these issues, the fundamental challenges of accurately estimating long-term R_D of PV systems due to the lack of extensive validation were investigated in this work, by analyzing the extent to which different pipeline techniques and models perform against synthetic PV system performance datasets of emulated linear-pattern degradation levels and known missing data rates.

The analysis performed in this study includes a sequence of extensive validation steps to determine R_D by applying different time series analytics to constructed PV system synthetic performance data with linear long-term degradation emulated patterns of 0.2%/yr to 2%/yr at intervals of 0.2%/year. In addition, different missing data rates were randomly imputed to the raw power datasets and to the PR monthly time series in order to emulate commonly exhibited communication and DAQ system errors. The robustness of the proposed R_D technique pipeline was further verified against actual field data acquired from the identical test-bench PV system and indoor standardized maximum power determination methods at STC.

The analysis showed that the accuracy of all techniques apart from CSD and STL, is affected by the evaluation duration with the highest calculated R_D deviations exhibited when ARIMA and OLS were applied to the 5-year evaluation period.

Prolonged noise events affected the accuracy of the R_D results more compared to short-period noise event imputed to raw power datasets. In particular, when the percentage of missing aggregated monthly PR values was $\leq 10\%$, the applied statistical techniques provided relatively accurate results. Moreover, all techniques outperformed the YOY at missing data rates of 20–40%.

Furthermore, the application of a change-point detection stage to validate whether deflection points exist is a crucial step in degradation analytical methods since the verification analysis demonstrated that the two-step linear regression technique provided more accurate results compared to the application of conventional statistical models on nonlinear degradation patterns.

Finally, the obtained results provided adequate information to form usage guidelines for the different degradation techniques under noisy conditions. In this domain, the methodological steps can be replicated to analyze the underlying degradation of PV power plant portfolios and accurately provide lifetime performance predictions. It should be noted here that the results exported from this study are based on the analysis of a single mono-c-Si PV system and thus further analysis is required and will be part of future work. To this end, future investigations will focus on several locations (with different climates) and different PV module technologies for deriving location- and technology-independent usage guidelines for the different degradation techniques under noisy conditions.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Irene Romero-Fiances: Formal analysis, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Andreas Livera:** Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Marios Theristis:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Visualization, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **George Makrides:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Joshua S. Stein:** Writing – review & editing. **Gustavo Nofuentes:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Juan de la Casa:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **George E. Georgiou:** Supervision, Project administration, Resources.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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